

PAPER CHROMATOGRAPHIC STUDIES OF SOME NATURAL COUMARINS

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Chromatographic technique has been applied for the separation and identification of 12 natural coumarins. From the results it appears that coumarins are to some extent separable and water appears to be the most suitable solvent for the purpose.

Partition paper chromatography has in recent years proved very useful in the detection, identification and separation of organic compounds of plant or animal origin. The method is also valuable in judging the homogeneity of compounds.

The detection of coumarins by means of this technique is of recent interest (Sevendson, *Pharm. Acta Helv.*, 1952, 27, 44; Riedel and Neugebauer, *Monatsh.*, 1952, 83, 1083). In course of studies of naturally occurring polyphenols involved in the enzymatic browning by potato polyphenolase, Swain (*Biochem. J.*, 1953, 53, 200) applied this method for the detection of minute quantities of coumarins. In course of our work on the isolation and identification of small quantities of coumarins present in plant materials, need was felt for a further study of paper chromatography of some natural coumarins.

For this purpose, twelve natural coumarins, which we could secure, were chosen. These are listed in Table I.

Name.		TABLE I	*Occurrence.
1.	Ayapin	...	<i>Eupatorium ayapana</i> , Vent.
2.	Bergapten	...	<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i> (Christm.), Swingle.
3.	Ryakangelicin	...	<i>Angelica glabra</i> , Makino.
4.	Coumarin	...	<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i> , Linn.
5*	Ferulin	...	<i>Ferula alliacea</i> , Boiss.
6.	Limettin	...	<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i> (Christm.), Swingle (Khastagir, this Journal, 1947, 25, 421).
7.	Luvangetin	...	<i>Luvanga scandens</i> , Ham.
8.	Marmesin	...	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> , Correa.
9.	Marmisin	...	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> , Correa. (Chatterjee & Chowdhury, <i>Naturwiss.</i> , 1955, 32, 512).
10.	Murrayin	...	<i>Murraya esotica</i> , Linn.
11.	Pimpinellin	...	<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i> , Linn.
12.	Seselin	...	<i>Seseli indicum</i> , W & A.

* Dean, *Fortschritte der Chemie organischer Naturstoffe*, 1952, IX, pp. 235-291.

The above coumarins were subjected to paper chromatography by the uni-dimensional ascending technique with a number of solvent systems of which twenty one, which ensured reproducible results, were finally chosen. The solvent systems are mentioned in Table II.

TABLE II

1. Water		12. Formamide-ammonia*-water	... 2:3:7
2. Methanol-acetic acid-water	... 16:3:1	13. Acetone-petroleum ether-water	... 5:3:4
3. Methanol-formamide-water	... 1:2:7		(lower phase)
4. Methanol-formic acid-water	... 16:3:1	14. Petroleum ether-benzene-water	... 15:1:5
5. Methanol-ammonia*-water	... 6:1:3	15. Do	... 10:1:3
6. Water-dioxane	... 9:1	16. <i>iso</i> Propanol-ammonia*-water	... 3:2:5
7. Do	... 1:3	17. <i>iso</i> Propanol-ammonia*	... 10:1
8. Ethyleneglycol-water	... 1:24	18. <i>n</i> -Butanol (saturated with water)	... 4:1:1
9. Do	... 1:9	19. <i>n</i> -Butanol-water-acetic acid	... 4:1:1
10. Pyridine-water	... 3:97	20. Acetic acid	... 70%
11. Pyridine-ammonia*-water	... 1:2:7	21. <i>tert.</i> -Butanol-ammonia*	... 9:1

*Aqueous ammonia solution of sp. gr. 0.91.

EXPERIMENTAL

Method.—A solution of the coumarin (5 mg. in 2 c.c. ethanol) was, as a rule, used. Where the solubility was low, a saturated ethanolic solution was employed. The primary spots, delivered from a micro-pipette on to the filter paper, represented approximately $10\ \mu$ l of the solution or 0.025 microgram of the substance. The arrangement and procedure were the same as those described by Burina and Banerjee (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 135). Whatman filter paper No. 1 was used. Solvents used were of the purest quality available. In the cases of mixed immiscible solvents, the upper phase was used except where mentioned otherwise (*vide e.g.*, solvent system 13). The experiments were conducted at room temperature (25° – 31°). Each experiment was repeated 3 to 6 times under approximately the same conditions.

The spots in the chromatogram were observed under the ultraviolet light (Chromatolite 2537Å). Treatment of the paper with ammonia vapour or 2*N*-NaOH solution intensified the fluorescence under the ultraviolet light. The R_f values are recorded in Table III, while Table IV shows the nature of fluorescence observed with different spray reagents.

The spots were usually elongated. Trailing of spots was generally noticed with water as the solvent. This effect was most marked in the case of luvangetin with solvent systems 8 and 9, so that no R_f value could be calculated. The effects were generally much less in acidic solvents. Seselin and pimpinellin gave two spots each in solvent system 11. This abnormality is believed to be due to partial opening of the lactone ring in presence of the basic solvent.

After having determined the R_f values of individual coumarins in the different solvent systems, attempts were made to separate and identify each of the constituents from a mixture of all the twelve coumarins.

The results of experiments with mixtures of coumarins are shown in Table III. It is evident that ferulin, bergapten and murrayin could be separated and identified in solvent systems, 1 and 6. In the solvent system 1, four other distinct spots were also noticed. These had R_f values 0.38, 0.49, 0.55, 0.67 respectively, and proved (from observations of the nature of fluorescence) to be due to mixtures of coumarins having similar R_f values.

TABLE III
R_f values of coumarins in different solvents.

Coumarins.	Solvent No.										R _f	
	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.		
Avapin.	0.48	0.73	0.76	0.79	0.68	0.63	0.95	0.50	0.56	0.59	0.72	0.74
Bergapten	0.20	0.74	0.65	0.68	0.63	0.41	0.98	0.17	0.26	0.32	0.78	0.53
Byakangelicin	0.54	0.75	0.85	0.69	No spot	0.71	No spot	0.55	0.62	0.67	0.72	No spot
Coumarin	No spot	No spot	No spot	No spot	Do	No spot	Do	No spot	No spot	No spot	0.89	0.91
Ferulin	0.0	0.76	Do	0.95	0.84	0.0	0.93	Do	Do	Do	0.83	No spot
Limonin	0.36	0.73	0.76	0.68	0.73	0.57	0.98	0.47	0.4	0.56	0.76	0.65
Louvaugetin	0.46	0.79	0.81	0.72	0.82	0.69	0.68	Very long dragging.	0.86	0.89	0.89	0.76
Marmesin	0.66	0.76	0.90	0.89	0.76	0.77	0.95	0.67	0.70	0.78	0.83	0.81
Marmirin	0.64	0.78	0.91	0.90	0.71	0.76	0.97	0.65	0.73	0.73	0.79	0.79
Murrayin	0.76	0.61	0.95	0.74	0.72	0.82	0.91	0.75	0.77	0.81	0.92	0.87
Pimpinellin	0.38	0.79	0.80	0.89	0.77	0.61	0.97	0.43	0.54	0.59	0.76	0.72
Seselin	0.43	0.79	0.84	0.90	0.79	0.62	0.97	0.44	0.54	0.55	0.79	0.76
Mixture	0.00	0.59	Over lapp-	0.75	0.69	0.60	0.90	Over lapp-	0.36	0.28	0.71	0.59 ^a
	0.18	0.69	ing fluores-	0.84	0.77	0.41 ^b	0.98	ing fluo-	0.32	0.44	0.84	0.79
	0.37	0.82	cent zones	0.97	0.83	0.52	rescent	0.52	0.57	0.57	0.92	
	0.49					0.70	zones	0.56	0.83			
	0.55					0.74		0.72				
	0.67					0.81						
	0.77 ^c											
Expt. temp.	30° ± 1°	28.5° ± 1°	30° ± 1°	29.5° ± 1°	29.5° ± 1°	30° ± 1°	30° ± 1°	29.5° ± 1°	30° ± 1°	29.5° ± 1°	29.5° ± 1°	29.5° ± 1°

TABLE III (contd.)
R₁ values of coumarins in different solvents.

Solvent No. <i>Fig.</i>	14.	15.	16.	17.	18 ^a .	18 ^b .	19.	20.	21.
Coumarins									
-Alypin	0.81	0.62	0.74	0.80	0.92	0.08	0.92	0.72	0.96
Bergapten	0.82	0.78	0.76	0.86	0.94	0.95	0.92	0.49	0.96
Byakangelicin	No spot	0.0	No spot	0.83	0.91	0.90	0.90	0.82	0.95
Commarrin	Do	No spot	Do	No spot	No spot	No spot	0.74	No spot	No spot
Ferulin	0.79	0.75	0.98	0.96	0.98	0.97	0.82	Do	0.95
Limettin	0.87	0.73	0.84	0.68	0.95	0.97	0.91	0.68	0.97
Lavangetin	0.93	0.68	0.88	0.69	0.96	0.97	0.93	0.82	0.95
Maremsin	0.90	0.66	0.88	0.85	0.92	0.97	0.91	0.87	0.96
Marrtin	0.91	0.65	0.90	0.86	0.93	0.96	0.94	0.84	0.96
Murrayin	0.83	0.0	0.84 ^d	0.33	0.46	0.38	0.56	0.93	0.40
Pimpinellin	0.92	0.92	0.86	0.82	0.93	0.95	0.95	0.74	0.96
Seselin	0.92	0.93	0.84	0.74	0.93	0.95	0.95	0.74	0.97
Mixture									
	0.78	0.0	0.75	0.33 ^a	0.44 ^c	0.39 ^d	Floures- cent zones overlapping.	Continuous fluorescent zone.	0.39 ^e
	0.85	0.74	0.80	0.62	0.94	0.93			0.92
	0.93	0.92	0.85	0.74					
		0.98	0.91	0.86					
		0.93	0.99 ^b	0.95 ^b					
Expt. temp.	29.5° ± 1°	25.5° ± 1.5°	27.5° ± 1°	28° ± 1°	30.5° ± 1°	30° ± 5°	29.5° ± 1°	30° ± 1°	29.5° ± 1°

Remarks : a : bergapten, b : ferulin, c : murrayin ; d : ordinary ; e : borated.
 Figs. 1, 2 21 indicate the solvent systems mentioned in Table II.

In other solvents a similar situation was experienced with the mixtures. With some of the solvents, however, a few of the coumarins produced spots which were traced to a particular component of the mixture (vide Table III). These are bergapten, ferulin and murrayin.

TABLE IV
Colour produced by chromogenic spray.

	Ultraviolet fluorescence.			
	Untreated	NH ₃ vapour.	2N-NaOH solution.	1% KMnO ₄ solution.
Avapin	v	br-b	b-g	g-y
Bergapten	yb	f-y	y	y-bn
Byakangelicin	bn	f-bn	l-bn	y-bn
Coumarin	...	q	gb	g-y
Ferulin	q-bn	deep bn (y*)	s (y*)	g-y
Limeftin	vb	br-y	b	g-y
Luvangetin	yb	yb	br-y (y*)	g-y
Marmesin	vb	vb	l-b	y-bn
Marmin	vb	br-b	b	y-bn
Murrayin	vb	b	g-y	y-bn
Pimpinellin	pb	gb	y-g	g-y
Seselin	pb	gb	y-g	g-y

(f-faint, l-light, p-pale, br-bright, v-violet, vb-violetish blue, yb-yellowish blue, bn-brown, y-yellow, b-blue, gb-greenish blue, g-green, s-scarlet, q-queching, * ordinary light)

DISCUSSION

It will be apparent from the results that incorporation of purely organic solvents to water enhances the R_f values of coumarins. Increase of R_f values of coumarins has also been noticed after addition of ammonia to water-pyridine system.

The addition of hydroxylic solvents (*n*-butanol, isopropanol) to water lowers the R_f values of murrayin, while incorporation of acetone or pyridine to water increases the same. When ammoniacal isopropanol is added to water, similar effect is observed. The lowering of R_f values has only been observed in the case of the glucoside, murrayin, by the use of borate paper. This result is consistent with the observations of Wachmeister (*Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1951, 5, 976) and Swain (*loc. cit.*) that lowering of R_f values of coumarin glucosides may result due to chelation of the glucose residue with borate.

The behaviour of byakangelicin and ferulin, which are very close in their molecular structure, is interesting. Ferulin is $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl- $\beta\gamma$ -epoxyallyl ether of 8-hydroxy-5-methoxyfurano-2':3'-6:7-coumarin, while byakangelicin is the corresponding dihydroxy compound. In water system ferulin shows no movement, while byakangelicin has R_f value of 0.54. In solvent system 14, byakangelicin does not move, while ferulin registers R_f value of 0.75.

It has been reported by Swain (*loc. cit.*) that spots of coumarin could only be detected in the ultraviolet light after spraying the developed chromatogram with 2N-sodium

hydroxide. In the present investigations spots of coumarin were observed without the use of spray reagents under ultraviolet light, when the solvent systems were pyridine-ammonia-water, formamide-ammonia-water, and *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water.

It appears from the present investigation that coumarins are to some extent separable and the most suitable solvent is water. Using water for this purpose, the R_f values were found to be generally less than 0.75. This supports, from theoretical considerations, the view that separation of coumarins by filter-paper chromatography probably involves factors other than pure liquid-liquid partition (Consden *et al.* *Biochem. J.*, 1944, **38**, 224 ; Swain, *loc.cit.*).

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